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1. Introduction

The University of Cyprus (UCY), as a forward-looking research-performing institution, is committed to reforming its research assessment practices in line with the principles of the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA). In recent years, global discourse on

research evaluation has recognised the limitations of traditional metrics and rankings in capturing the full breadth and value of research activity. The UCY CoARA Action Plan (AP) emerges from this context, aiming to drive a cultural and structural transformation in how research and researchers are assessed, recognized, and supported.

As part of the **OSCAR project** (Open Science Collaboration for Research Career Advancement and Policy Innovation at UNIRI and UCY)—co-funded by Horizon Europe under the CoARA Boost Cascade Funding programme, UCY works in close collaboration with the University of Rijeka (UNIRI) and the European Office of Cyprus (EOC) to develop and implement a robust, forward-thinking action plan.

The development of this Action Plan was informed by the “CoARA Action Plan Development Guidelines” produced by UNIRI and integrates insights from institutional gap analyses, as well as best practices within the CoARA community, and the shared learnings from the OSCAR partnership. It places particular emphasis on the integration of Open Science (OS) principles, the development of qualitative and contextual evaluation frameworks, and the promotion of equity and inclusiveness across all research career stages.

2. Vision and Strategic Objectives

The vision underpinning this plan is the establishment of a research culture at UCY that is open, responsible, inclusive, and supportive of diverse research contributions. Research assessment is not only an institutional function but also a key element of academic culture and researcher development.

The overarching strategic objectives of UCY's CoARA Action Plan are:

- To develop inclusive and context-sensitive frameworks for researcher evaluation;
- To align research careers and progression with principles of transparency, diversity, and openness;
- To enhance capacity building through training, awareness, valorization and participation in the CoARA network;
- To institutionalise Open Science practices within all assessment procedures;
- To serve as a national model of reform, influencing broader policy change through strategic engagement with national authorities.

These objectives reflect the UCY commitment to the CoARA core and supporting commitments, especially those concerning the recognition of research diversity, qualitative evaluation, and responsible metrics.

3. Institutional Context and Readiness

The University of Cyprus is a research-intensive institution that has demonstrated consistent growth in both its research outputs and its role as a policy-shaping actor within the national

and European research landscape. UCY is a signatory of the CoARA agreement. The agreement was signed on May 10, 2023, demonstrating their commitment to reforming research assessment practices and aligning with European Research Area (ERA) priorities. Furthermore, UCY also participates in the CoARA National Chapter Cyprus, alongside the European Office of Cyprus.

As a member of the Young Universities for the Future of Europe (YUFE) alliance and participant in initiatives such as the Human Resources Strategy for Researchers (HRS4R), UCY has developed a foundational commitment to excellence, inclusivity, and openness in research.

UCY's institutional framework reflects a progressive orientation toward responsible research and innovation. The Research and Innovation Support Service (RISS) operates as the central hub for coordinating research-related activities and liaising with both internal stakeholders and external bodies such as the European Commission and national authorities. This unit is pivotal in aligning UCY's internal policies with European priorities, including those enshrined in the European Research Area (ERA), DORA, and now CoARA.

The university also benefits from strong research infrastructure through its Centres of Excellence—such as the KIOS Research and Innovation Centre—which exemplify interdisciplinary research and collaboration with societal stakeholders. SInnoPSis, UCY's scientific working group on research-on-research, adds methodological depth to the institution's reform initiatives by applying scientific and empirical rigour and meta-research techniques to inform research assessment practices. Within the OSCAR partnership, SInnoPSis has developed a guidelines document titled "*Scientific Guide in Validating CoARA Adjustment Practices Using Research-in-Research*" to inform science-driven implementation of the CoARA Action Plan.

In preparation for the CoARA Action Plan, UCY conducted an internal mapping exercise to assess current assessment practices, researcher career progression policies, and open science adoption. This baseline assessment has highlighted both institutional strengths and areas for improvement, particularly the need to develop a consistent approach to evaluating diverse research contributions and to support early-career researchers more systematically.

Thus, UCY enters the CoARA reform process with a robust internal capacity, clear strategic alignment, and a culture increasingly oriented towards transparency, inclusiveness, and excellence.

4. Categories of Actions in the Plan

The core of this Action Plan is the **Action Plan Table**, which organises proposed actions into key categories. Each category addresses a strategic aspect of the assessment reform process, reflecting both institutional priorities and CoARA's commitments.

4.1. Careers / Researchers

Actions in this category focus on supporting researchers, especially Early Career Researchers (ECRs), by establishing transparent, flexible, and inclusive career pathways. These actions aim to redefine researcher development beyond traditional metrics, incorporating mentoring, cross-sector mobility, and career stage mapping.

4.2. Assessment

This category involves reforming evaluation mechanisms at the level of individuals, research units, and internal funding schemes. Actions target the implementation of narrative-based CVs, peer review enhancements, and evaluation guides rooted in CoARA principles. It also includes pilots that allow UCY to test and iterate its assessment tools and criteria.

4.3. Training

Recognising the importance of skills development, the training category includes capacity-building initiatives such as workshops on Open Science, responsible metrics, and research ethics. These sessions aim to upskill researchers, evaluators, and managers and embed responsible assessment practices at all levels of UCY.

4.4. Governance

Actions here concern institutional support structures necessary for sustained implementation. Examples include the formation of the UCY Open Science Committee and the development of institutional policies for responsible research and assessment. These mechanisms will provide oversight and ensure coherence across initiatives.

4.5. Feedback / Monitoring

Robust mechanisms to collect and incorporate feedback are essential for iterative development. This category includes surveys, stakeholder consultations, and implementation monitoring, ensuring that actions remain grounded in lived researcher experiences and institutional needs.

4.6. National Policy / Engagement

These actions reflect UCY's ambition to act as a national leader in reforming research assessment in Cyprus. To this end, it has undertaken the leadership in co-chairing the CoARA National Chapter for Cyprus. Through workshops, advocacy efforts, and participation in CoARA working groups, UCY will contribute to shaping national-level frameworks and foster alignment between institutional and policy-level reforms.

5. UCY CoARA Action Plan 2025-2028

5.1 Table of Actions

No	Action	Related CoARA Commitments	Category	Year	Quarter	Responsibility
1	Mapping the academic staff members of UCY to R1-R4 career stages	1	Careers/Researchers	2025	Q3	RISS
2	Set of recommendations for improving research careers of ECRs	1, 6, 2	Careers/Researchers	2025	Q3	Vice Rector of Academic Affairs, Ad-Hoc Committee for Academic Recruitment & Research Careers, RISS
3	Conduct an internal readiness mapping to assess UCY's preparedness for implementing research assessment reforms, based on criteria such as metrics use, evaluator training, and alignment with CoARA principles	1, 6, 9	Assessment	2025	Q4	RISS

No	Action	Related CoARA Commitments	Category	Year	Quarter	Responsibility
4	Create guidelines on UCY's official criteria for recruitment, promotion, and funding to reflect narrative evaluation, openness, and societal relevance, starting by developing a narrative-based CV.	1, 2, 10	Assessment	2025	Q4	RISS, KIOS Centre of Excellence, SInnoPSis
5	Open Science training sessions including Open Access, Open Data, Legal & Ethical Frameworks, reproducibility of research and Citizen Engagement	1, 7	Training	2025	Q4	Library, RISS (YUFE 2030)
6	Creation of an Open Science Committee at UCY	5, 7	Governance	2025	Q4	Vice Rector of Academic Affairs, Library, RISS
7	Creation of a "Scientific Guide in Validating CoARA Adjustment Practices Using Research-in-Research"		Feedback/Monitoring	2025	Q4	SInnoPSis

No	Action	Related CoARA Commitments	Category	Year	Quarter	Responsibility
8	A guide on how to evaluate the small research grants scheme based on CoARA principles has been prepared and will be piloted at UCY	2, 6	Assessment	2026	Q1	Research Committee, RISS (YUFE 2030)
9	A guide on how to evaluate UCY research units based on CoARA principles has been prepared and will be piloted at UCY	2, 6.1	Assessment	2026	Q4	Research Committee, RISS (YUFE 2030)
10	A survey for receiving feedback on the application process and assessment criteria of internal research grants of UCY	7, 9, 10	Feedback/Monitoring	2026	Q4	RISS, SInnoPSis
11	Creation of a Responsible Research and Research Assessment Policy, to be shared with UCY research assessors.	6, 9	Institutional Policy (separate procedure of Assessment)	2026	Q4	RISS (YUFE 2030)

No	Action	Related CoARA Commitments	Category	Year	Quarter	Responsibility
12	Carry out research related to research assessment and feed the results and recommendations into the relevant policies of UCY	10	Feedback/Monitoring	2026	Q4	SInnoPSis
13	A pilot on improving research careers not only within academia but also towards a cross-sectoral career path (implement recommendations from the European Framework for Research Careers (RCF) to improve research career progression and mobility within UCY)	1, 6.2	Careers/Researchers	2027	Q4	RISS, Career Office
14	Policy Recommendations based on CoARA principles and the outcomes of the thematic working groups	8, 9	National Policy / Engagement	2027	Q4	SInnoPSis

No	Action	Related CoARA Commitments	Category	Year	Quarter	Responsibility
15	Participate and contribute to the CoARA Working Group "Responsible Metrics and Indicators (RMI)"	2, 3, 6, 8, 10	CoARA	2028	Q4	SInnoPSis
16	Launch institutional consultations with researchers at all career stages, research managers, and HR to co-create and validate proposed reform actions	10	Feedback/Monitoring	2027	Q2	RISS, HR Service
17	Embed responsible research and assessment principles into selected MSc and PhD programmes, using structured learning resources		Training	2026	Q4	RISS, Graduate School (YUFE 2030)
18	Publish an annual implementation report with indicators, progress review, and stakeholder feedback, to monitor and guide reform uptake	9	Feedback/Monitoring	2026-2028	Q4	RISS Research Committee Open Science Committee

No	Action	Related CoARA Commitments	Category	Year	Quarter	Responsibility
19	Engage with national authorities and research funders to advocate for alignment of national evaluation frameworks with responsible assessment practices.		National Policy / Engagement	2026	Q3	RISS, EOC
20	Design an awareness campaign on CoARA approach and processes. Start by hosting an institutional or national-level workshop to share UCY's experience with responsible research assessment and stimulate uptake across the academic community.	8	National Policy / Engagement	2026	Q1	RISS, EOC
21	Support initiatives to inform crucial institutional actors (court judges, policymakers) about appropriate research assessment and the pitfalls of one-dimensional adoption of quantitative criteria alone.	2, 8, 10	National Policy / Engagement	2027	Q1	RISS, SInnoPSis

6. Implementation

Successful implementation of the Action Plan requires strong leadership, coordination, and resource allocation. UCY will adopt a **participatory approach** involving actors at all levels—including researchers at R1–R4 career stages, administrative staff, librarians, and academic leaders. The implementation will be led by the Research and Innovation Support Service (RISS), with oversight from the Vice Rector of Academic Affairs.

Each action in the AP Table has a clear timeline (organised by year and quarter), defined responsibilities, and stated dependencies. Actions are grouped into short-term (2025), medium-term (2026–2027), and long-term (2028) initiatives, ensuring a realistic and sustainable pacing of reforms.

In terms of governance, the Research Committee with the support of a dedicated **Open Science Committee** will coordinate policy and practice changes related to OS and RA reform. Progress will be reviewed annually, with results presented in publicly available implementation reports.

7. Stakeholder Engagement

To ensure the successful and systemic implementation of its CoARA Action Plan 2025–2028, the University of Cyprus (UCY) will adopt a Quadruple Helix approach to stakeholder engagement. This model—encompassing academia, government, civil society, and entrepreneurship—will guide participatory reform across institutional and national levels. Stakeholder collaboration will be built into the design, execution, and monitoring of responsible research assessment practices, reinforcing UCY’s role as both a reforming institution and a national catalyst for change.

7.1 Academia

UCY will prioritize the active involvement of the academic community in shaping and implementing the Action Plan. Researchers at all **R1–R4 career stages** will participate in consultations, pilot activities, and feedback mechanisms. To strengthen collective reform across the national academic system, UCY will also engage other public and private higher education and research institutions in Cyprus. This broader academic collaboration will be facilitated through the CoARA National Chapter Cyprus and coordinated policy dialogues.

UCY will embed engagement mechanisms such as:

- Departmental forums and co-creation workshops with researchers, doctoral coordinators, and HR officers.
- Institutional consultations to validate actions such as narrative-based CVs, updated promotion criteria, and training modules on responsible metrics.
- Establishment of the Open Science Committee as a cross-functional advisory body ensuring academic ownership of reform.

By fostering cross-institutional partnerships, UCY will ensure that reforms are coherent, scalable, and collectively endorsed by the national research community.

7.2 Government

Governmental actors will play a pivotal role in the implementation and policy alignment of UCY's CoARA Action Plan. UCY will deepen its engagement with the **Deputy Ministry of Research, Innovation and Digital Policy** to harmonise institutional reforms with Cyprus' national research strategy and legislative frameworks. This collaboration will support the uptake of responsible assessment criteria in national research funding and academic promotion policies.

At the **European level**, UCY will liaise with relevant EU institutions and bodies, including the European Commission, to ensure that its reform process aligns with the broader European Research Area (ERA), Horizon Europe policy priorities, and CoARA Working Group outputs. Through its participation in EU-funded initiatives such as OSCAR, UCY will also contribute to shaping and sharing best practices across Europe.

UCY will initiate:

- Strategic roundtables and briefings with national authorities.
- Policy coordination activities through the European Office of Cyprus (EOC).
- Contributions to EU-wide efforts in research assessment reform, especially through its involvement in thematic CoARA Working Groups.

This multi-level government engagement will ensure policy coherence, resource mobilisation, and alignment with pan-European research reform agendas.

7.3 Civil Society

As part of its commitment to open, inclusive, and socially responsive research, UCY will involve civil society actors in its assessment reform journey. These stakeholders will be invited to contribute perspectives on how research quality and impact should be defined in relation to societal needs.

UCY will:

- Integrate citizen engagement elements into Open Science training and evaluation processes.
- Include civil society organisations (CSOs) in workshops and national-level CoARA events aimed at raising awareness and gathering input on reform initiatives.
- Promote the societal relevance of research assessment by opening feedback channels beyond academia.

By embedding the values and expectations of civil society into the Action Plan, UCY will strengthen public trust and make research evaluation more accountable and context-sensitive.

7.4 Entrepreneurship

Entrepreneurial stakeholders—**startups, innovation clusters, and industry partners**—will be critical in shaping reform actions that reflect cross-sectoral career mobility and applied research value. UCY will work to ensure that research assessment criteria capture contributions that drive innovation, commercialisation, and societal application.

Key initiatives will include:

- Collaborating with UCY's Centres of Excellence (e.g., KIOS) to pilot assessment methods that recognise interdisciplinary and industry-engaged research.
- Implementing actions that support career progression pathways extending beyond academia, in line with the European Framework for Research Careers.
- Engaging entrepreneurial partners in advisory roles to co-design training content and mobility support schemes.

These actions will help UCY align its research assessment system with the evolving role of universities as innovation and knowledge transfer hubs.

By operationalising stakeholder engagement through the Quadruple Helix model, UCY will ensure that the CoARA Action Plan 2025–2028 is inclusive, effective, and anchored in Cyprus's wider research, policy, societal, and innovation ecosystems.

8. Monitoring and Evaluation

Monitoring and evaluation (M&E) are fundamental to the success and sustainability of UCY's CoARA Action Plan. These mechanisms will ensure that the reform process remains evidence-based, adaptive, and aligned with institutional and stakeholder expectations. The approach to M&E will be structured, participatory, and methodologically rigorous, reflecting UCY's broader commitment to quality assurance and transparency.

At the core of this strategy is the establishment of an **institutional monitoring framework**, supported by digital tools such as dashboards and centralised data collection systems. For each action in the Action Plan both qualitative and quantitative measurable indicators will be assigned, which will be used to track progress, identify implementation barriers, and recalibrate interventions when necessary. The indicators will assess not only completion status but also qualitative outcomes, such as improved researcher satisfaction, diversity in evaluation criteria, and uptake of narrative CVs. For this point the Research Assessment Framework (RAF) developed in the context of Open and Universal Science (**OPUS**) Project, to which UCY participated as a pilot organisation, will be utilised.

To ensure objectivity and continuous learning, UCY will also draw on the expertise of its **SInnoPSis working group**, whose research-on-research expertise will be applied to validate the relevance, effectiveness, and fairness of new assessment practices. The principles behind these actions are embedded in the scientific guide "Scientific Guide in Validating CoARA Adjustment Practices Using Research-in-Research" SInnoPSis will periodically conduct surveys, interviews, and desk research to evaluate the adoption and impact of the reforms, including comparison with baseline data.

The results of these evaluations will feed into **annual implementation reports**, which will be shared with internal governance bodies (e.g., Research Committee, Open Science Committee, Senate, Rector's Council) and external stakeholders including the CoARA community and the Deputy Ministry of Research, Innovation and Digital Policy. These reports will include policy recommendations, case studies, and forward-looking priorities for scaling successful practices.

Feedback loops will also be built into the M&E framework. Researchers and staff will be able to submit feedback anonymously or through structured sessions. This iterative process will help UCY remain agile and responsive to stakeholder concerns while promoting a culture of shared accountability and continuous improvement.

9. Challenges and Mitigation

While the proposed CoARA Action Plan places the University of Cyprus (UCY) on a transformative path, several internal and external challenges may hinder its smooth implementation. Understanding and proactively addressing these is essential to ensure long-term success.

9.1 Internal Challenges

a. Resistance to Change

A major internal hurdle is cultural resistance, particularly among senior academic staff accustomed to traditional evaluation models based on journal impact factors or publication counts. These stakeholders may view the shift to narrative CVs and qualitative assessments as a threat to established academic hierarchies.

b. Disciplinary Variability

Different faculties and research disciplines may have varying expectations and norms. For instance, researchers in STEM may be more reliant on high-impact journal publications, whereas Humanities scholars may prioritise, books, monographs or societal impact—making it difficult to apply uniform assessment criteria.

c. Career Stage Concerns

ECRs may feel especially vulnerable during this transition, uncertain how reforms will impact their progression, recruitment, or funding opportunities.

d. Peer Review Load and Quality

Implementing more peer-led, narrative-based evaluations may increase workload and costs and raise concerns over consistency and quality of assessments. Ensuring fair, knowledgeable, and non-biased review processes within the institution may prove complex.

9.2 Mitigation Measures (Internal)

- **Awareness and Capacity Building:** UCY could launch a comprehensive awareness campaign using testimonials, workshops, and policy briefs to explain the rationale and benefits of responsible research assessment (RRA).
- **Accommodation of heterogeneity:** Differences across disciplines in research assessment will be acknowledged and accommodated based on scientific principles (e.g. driven by meta-research).

- **Inclusive Design Processes:** Cross-disciplinary and cross-career-stage stakeholder consultations could be built into all design and implementation stages to ensure diverse perspectives shape the reforms.
- **Support Structures for ECRs:** Dedicated training, mentoring programmes and clear guidance documents could be developed to ensure ECRs are informed and supported through the transition.
- **Structured Peer Review Systems:** The creation of institutional guidelines, pilot testing of new review formats, and consideration of international reviewer pools will help maintain quality and consistency.

9.3 External Challenges

a. Misalignment with National Policies/Legislations

Cyprus's national funding schemes and academic promotion regulations may not fully align with CoARA principles, creating a disconnect between UCY's institutional reforms and external evaluation expectations. Furthermore, certain elements of assessment policy may be tied to national or legislative mandates, restricting UCY's flexibility in applying reform across all levels and disciplines.

b. Sectoral Engagement Gaps

There may be insufficient participation from civil society and the private sector in shaping or understanding new assessment models, which could hinder cross-sectoral impact and uptake.

c. Resource and Infrastructure Constraints

Successful reform requires sustained financial, administrative, and technological support—especially for digital monitoring tools and training platforms, which may be constrained under current budgets.

9.4 Mitigation Measures (External)

- **Policy Engagement and Advocacy:** UCY could intensify dialogue with the Deputy Ministry of Research, Innovation and Digital Policy to align national frameworks with CoARA principles, leveraging its role in the CoARA National Chapter of Cyprus. Moreover, through EOC, UCY could collaborate with EU actors to influence broader policy developments and share best practices.
- **Public and Private Stakeholder Involvement:** UCY could expand its engagement with civil society and entrepreneurial stakeholders via workshops, citizen science components in training, and co-design of mobility and innovation metrics.
- **Resource Mobilisation:** Targeted funding proposals (e.g., Horizon Europe, national grants) could be developed to secure dedicated resources for implementing digital infrastructure, monitoring systems, and training programmes.

By systematically addressing both internal and external challenges, and embedding specific mitigation strategies within the Action Plan, UCY enhances the feasibility, legitimacy, and sustainability of its transition to a responsible research assessment framework.

10. Way Forward

This Action Plan is a living document, designed to evolve as the reform process unfolds. The flexibility and responsiveness built into the implementation model will allow UCY to adapt to institutional feedback, emerging CoARA standards, and external policy changes.

By aligning institutional practices with global efforts for responsible research assessment, UCY is not only improving internal processes but also contributing to shaping a more equitable and transparent research ecosystem in Cyprus and the broader European research area.

The long-term goal is to mainstream these practices into all UCY operations—making responsible assessment the norm rather than the exception.